

MAPPING FUTURE FLOOD AND HEAT DISADVANTAGE IN GREAT BRITAIN:
AN ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF ADAPTATION POLICIES IN PROJECTED
HOTSPOTS AT A LOCAL SCALE

By

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This paper is accepted as conforming
to the required standard

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Appendix A

Search Terms and Boolean Logic Combinations Used for Literature Review

National Literature on Background Information		
Base search term		“climate change” AND (“United Kingdom” OR “Great Britain”)
Added search terms	1	AND “assessment” AND (“vulnerability” OR “inequality” OR “poverty” OR “justice” OR “injustice” OR “disadvantage”)
	2	AND “statistics” AND (“vulnerability” OR “inequality” OR “poverty” OR “justice” OR “injustice” OR “disadvantage”)
	3	AND (“adaptation” OR “adapt” OR “resilience” or “resilient”)
	4	AND “assessment” AND (“risk” OR “flood risk” OR “impact” OR “vulnerability” OR “strategic”)
	5	AND (“local authority” OR “LA” OR “council” OR “level” OR “subnational” OR “district” OR “authorities”)
	6	AND (“strategy” OR “plan” OR “action” OR “green”)
	7	AND “heat” AND “health” AND (“impact” OR “effects” OR “concern” or “issue”)
	8	AND (“extreme events” OR “heatwave” OR “heat” OR “flood”)
	9	AND (“weather” OR “climate”) AND (“projected” or “future” or “expected” or “projection”)
	10	AND (“legislation” OR “laws” OR “policy”)
International Literature on Background information		
Base search term		“climate change”
	11	AND (“global scale” OR “adaptation”)

Added search	12	AND (“government” or “governance” OR “level” OR “policy”)
terms	13	AND (“cumulative effects” OR “cascading” OR “compounding” OR “tipping point”)
National and International Literature on Adaptation Gaps		
Base search	14	“Climate Change” AND (“Adaptation” OR “Adapt”) AND (“measure” OR “policy” OR “policies” OR “plan” OR “strategy” OR “action” OR “state of”)
Added search	14	AND (“insufficient” OR “lack” OR “unsatisfactory” OR “issue” OR “barrier” OR “gap”) AND (“United Kingdom” OR “Great Britain”)
terms	15	AND (“insufficient” OR “lack” OR “unsatisfactory” OR “issue” OR “barrier” OR “gap”)
	16	AND (“insufficient” OR “lack” OR “unsatisfactory” OR “issue” OR “barrier” OR “gap”) AND (“cost” OR “opportunity”)
National Literature Adaptation Actions in Hotspots		
Base search		“UK” AND “climate change” AND “government” AND
terms		“UK” AND “climate change” AND (“resilience” OR “resilient” OR “adapt” OR “adaptation”) AND
		“UK” AND “climate” AND (“plan” OR “strategy” OR “action” OR “policy”) AND (“carbon” OR “route map” OR “net zero” OR “resilience” OR “resilient” OR “adapt” OR “adaptation”) AND
Added search	17-271	Each base search term was combined with the names of each of
terms		the 85 local authorities

Appendix B

B.1 Conceptual Framework for Assessing Socio-Spatial Vulnerability and Climate Disadvantage

Note. Lindley et al. (2011, p. 39).

B.2 *The Relationship Between Different Datasets Available in this Resource: Climate Disadvantage as a Measure of Socio-Spatial Vulnerability and Hazard-Exposure*

Note. Climate Just (2018, p. 4).

B.3 Framework of Analysis Used for Future Social Vulnerability to Flood Risk

Note. Sayers et al. (2017).

B.4 The Structure of the Neighbourhood Flood Vulnerability Index

Note. Sayers et al. (2017).

Appendix C

Sources Used for the Analysis of Adaptation Actions in the 85 Most Disadvantaged Local

Authorities

Barking and Dagenham (London)

Council declared a climate emergency. Plans to become carbon neutral by 2030.

<https://www.lbbd.gov.uk/news/barking-and-dagenham-council-declares-climate-emergency#:~:text=Barking%20and%20Dagenham%20Council%20has,become%20carbon%20neutral%20by%202030.&text=Barking%20and%20Dagenham%20Council%20has%20already%20taken%20a%20number,to%20reduce%20its%20carbon%20footprint.>

<https://www.lbbd.gov.uk/environment-strategies>

Action Plan.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/london-borough-of-barking-and-dagenham-33ed167.pdf>

Flood strategy and resilience forum and strategies.

<https://www.lbbd.gov.uk/flooding-strategy>

Birmingham

Sustainability West Midlands (SWM), in collaboration with the Environment Agency, has published a climate change adaptation plan for the West Midlands on Nov. 20, 2021.

<https://www.sustainabilitywestmidlands.org.uk/news/west-midlands-climate-change-adaptation-plan-published-today/>

On 11 June 2019 the council declared a climate emergency.

<https://birmingham.cmis.uk.com/Birmingham/Document.ashx?czJKcaeAi5tUFL1DTL2UE4zNRBcoShgo=Uli8HsKec3E%2bLHLkjpgDbPhS%2f5Lmp8bdHN5myI4k%2fBq1TqQ%2fTFCoFw%3d%3d&rUzwRPf%2bZ3zd4E7lkn8Lyw%3d%3d=pwRE6AGJFLDNlh225F5QMaQWcTPHwdhUfCZ%2fLUQzgA2uL5jNRG4jdQ%3d%3d&mCTIbCubSFfXsDGW9IXnlg%3d%3d=hFflUdN3100%3d&kCx1AnS9%2fpWZQ40DXFvdEw%3d%3d=hFflUdN3100%3d&uJovDxwdjMPoYv%2bAJvYtyA%3d%3d=ctNJff55vVA%3d&FgPIIEJYlotS%2bYGoBi5olA%3d%3d=NHdURQburHA%3d&d9Qjj0ag1Pd993jsyOJqFvmyB7X0CSQK=ctNJff55vVA%3d&WGewmoAfeNR9xqBux0r1Q8Za60lavYmz=ctNJff55vVA%3d&WGewmoAfeNQ16B2MHuCPMRKZMwaG1PaO=ctNJff55vVA%3d>

On 25 June 2019 the council's cabinet agreed to add a new priority to the Council Plan that takes a leading role in tackling climate change.

https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/info/50228/urban_centres_toolkit/2037/enhancing_local_identity_and_design/8

Climate Change Adaptation Action Plan (2012).

https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/downloads/file/1888/climate_change_adaptation_action_plan_2012

Development Plan.

https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/download/downloads/id/1412/cil_s06_infrastructure_delivery_plan.pdf

Environment and Sustainability.

[Environment and sustainability | Birmingham City Council](https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/environment-and-sustainability)

Planning.

<http://www.planvu.co.uk/bcc/written/bdp/cpt6.php#tp6>

Housing Plan (2020).

<https://www.birminghamal.gov/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/COB-Housing-Plan.pdf>

Transport Plan (2021).

https://www.birmingham.gov.uk/downloads/file/14861/birmingham_transport_strategy

Case Study.

<https://www.local.gov.uk/case-studies/birmingham-climate-change-and-vulnerable-communities>

Blackburn with Darwen

Climate change adaptation strategy.

<https://www.blackburn.gov.uk/environment/pollution/climate-change>

Climate Emergency Action Plan (2020).

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/blackburn-with-darwen-borough-council-68d0cbb.pdf>

<https://www.blackburn.gov.uk/sites/default/files/media/pdfs/UA-Climate%20Emergency%20Action%20Plan-Final1.pdf>

<https://www.blackburn.gov.uk/sites/default/files/media/pdfs/Climate-Change-Adaptation.pdf>

Blaenau Gwent

Decarbonisation Plan 2020 to 2030.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/blaenau-gwent-county-borough-council-23aadeb.pdf>

Biodiversity and Ecosystem Resilience Forward Plan (2019-2022).

<https://www.biodiversitywales.org.uk/File/703/en-GB>

Boston

Lincolnshire County Council (LCC) decided against declaring a Climate Emergency but committed to becoming carbon neutral by 2050.

<https://www.mybostonuk.com/boston-borough-council-declares-climate-emergency/>

[https://www.lincolnshire.gov.uk/directory-record/67743/climate-emergency-declaration#:~:text=Lincolnshire%20County%20Council%20\(LCC\)%20decided,the%20government%20target%20of%202030.](https://www.lincolnshire.gov.uk/directory-record/67743/climate-emergency-declaration#:~:text=Lincolnshire%20County%20Council%20(LCC)%20decided,the%20government%20target%20of%202030.)

<https://www.lincolnshire.gov.uk/green-masterplan/initial-plan-2020-2025/1>

Corporate Strategy. Climate Change Strategy for the Borough will also be developed in 2021-22.

<https://www.mybostonuk.com/environmental-protection-and-services/climate/>

Green Home Grants

<https://www.mybostonuk.com/climatechange/>

Brent (London)

Climate Emergency Strategy 2021-30

<https://democracy.brent.gov.uk/documents/s104356/7a.%20Appendix%201%20-Draft%20Brent%20Climate%20Emergency%20Strategy%202021-2030.pdf>

Climate Core strategy 2010

<https://www.brent.gov.uk/media/9432889/18.5.6.pdf>

Action plan 2012.

<https://www.brent.gov.uk/media/2002227/CCSG%20Action%20Plan%20-%20all%20groups,%20May%202012.pdf>

Climate emergency declared by Brent (10 July 2019). Aim for carbon neutrality by 2030.

<https://www.brent.gov.uk/council-news/july-2019/climate-emergency-declared-by-brent/>
<https://www.brent.gov.uk/media/16418130/appendix-a-brent-climate-ecological-emergency-strategy-2021-2030-1.pdf>

<https://www.brent.gov.uk/your-community/climate-emergency/our-response-to-the-climate-emergency/>

<https://www.brent.gov.uk/media/16418128/brent-climate-and-ecological-emergency-strategy-equality-impact-assessment-accessibility-version-1.pdf>

Bridgend

Carbon Targets.

<https://www.bridgend.gov.uk/news/leading-the-way-in-net-zero-carbon-targets/>

Low carbon communities.

<https://www.bridgend.gov.uk/residents/housing/low-carbon-communities/>

Pre-Plan

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/bridgend-county-borough-council-e9ce027.pdf>

Bristol, City of

In November 2018 the city councillors and Mayor declared a Climate Emergency.

One City Climate Strategy (PDF).

<https://www.bristol.gov.uk/policies-plans-strategies/council-action-on-climate-change>

One City Climate Strategy, a strategy for a carbon neutral, climate resilient Bristol by 2030.

<https://www.bristolonecity.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/one-city-climate-strategy.pdf>

Healthier Together Estates Climate Change Adaptation Plan 2021-2025 for Bristol, North Somerset, and South Gloucestershire.

<https://bnssghealthiertogether.org.uk/documents/healthier-together-estates-climate-change-adaptation-plan-2021-2025/>

Burnley

Council puts climate change on the agenda (2020 News).

<https://www.burnley.gov.uk/news/council-puts-climate-change-agenda>

2020 Air Quality Management.

<https://www.burnley.gov.uk/residents/planning/planning-policy/supplementary-planning-documents-spds/air-quality-management-protecting-health-and-addressing-climate-change-spd>

Cambridge

Climate Change and Sustainability.

<https://www.cambridge.gov.uk/climate-change-and-sustainability>

<https://www.cambridge.gov.uk/adapt-to-climate-change>

Cambridge City Council Climate Change Adaptation Plan 2018.

<https://www.cambridge.gov.uk/media/5996/climate-change-adaptation-plan.pdf>

Climate Change Strategy.

<https://www.cambridge.gov.uk/climate-change-strategy>

The University of Cambridge is building on its existing research and launching an ambitious new climate change initiative.

<https://www.zero.cam.ac.uk/>

Action Plan.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/cambridge-city-council-98f08f0.pdf>

Carbon Management Plan.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/cambridge-city-council-60e161e.pdf>

Camden (London)

Proposed Camden Climate Action Plan 2020-2025.

<https://www.camden.gov.uk/how-are-we-tackling-the-climate-crisis-in-camden->

Green Action for Change.

<https://www.camden.gov.uk/documents/20142/1458280/GAFC+Annual+review+2018+for+publication.pdf/a5e5ed25-79bc-5708-9a63-0e1ecdc0227a>

The Camden Climate Fund.

<https://www.camden.gov.uk/camden-climate-fund>

Carbon Scenarios 2010 Study.

<https://www.camden.gov.uk/documents/20142/0/Carbon+Scenarios+to+2030.pdf/215aa878-c657-10c7-4119-7a9f92dbb0f5>

Carmarthenshire

In February 2019, they declared a climate emergency, and made a commitment to becoming a net zero carbon local authority by 2030.

<https://www.carmarthenshire.gov.wales/home/council-democracy/net-zero-carbon/>

Climate Action Manifesto.

<https://www.carmarthenshire.gov.wales/home/council-democracy/net-zero-carbon/climate-action-manifesto/>

Net Zero Carbon Local Authority by 2030

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/carmarthenshire-county-council-225a2b3.pdf>

Project Zero Super Heroes.

<https://www.inyourarea.co.uk/news/carmarthenshire-council-launches-zero-carbon-climate-change-project/>

Clackmannanshire

Proposed Climate Change Strategy within the next 12 months.

<https://www.clacks.gov.uk/environment/climatechange/>

Council Statement.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/clackmannanshire-council-79621c6.pdf>

Strategies for embedding adaptation.

https://adaptationscotland.org.uk/application/files/7014/9442/9375/v2_2799_Casestudy_03Clacks.pdf

Coping with flooding.

<https://www.clacks.gov.uk/community/copingwithsnowandflooding/>

Sustainability and Climate Change Strategy (2010).

<https://www.clacks.gov.uk/environment/sustainabilityandclimate/>

Carbon Management Plan.

<https://www.clacks.gov.uk/document/meeting/1/258/2544.pdf>

Conwy

Climate Change.

<https://www.conwy.gov.uk/en/Council/Strategies-Plans-and-Policies/Climate-Change/Climate-Change.aspx>

Conwy County Borough Council Environmental Policy 2020.

<https://www.conwy.gov.uk/en/Council/Strategies-Plans-and-Policies/Climate-Change/assets/documents/Environmental-Policy-2020-v02.pdf>

Climate Commitments 2022.

<https://carbonbudget.manchester.ac.uk/reports/W06000003/>

Carbon Management Strategy 2019-24.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/conwy-county-borough-council-12f6fa5.pdf>

Coventry

2012 Climate Change Strategy.

https://www.coventry.gov.uk/downloads/download/1640/climate_change_strategy_for_coventry

Local Plan 2017.

https://www.coventry.gov.uk/downloads/file/25899/final_local_plan_december_2017

Croydon

Climate Change.

<https://www.croydon.gov.uk/planning-and-regeneration/planning-policy/planning-evidence-and-information/local-plan-evidence-topic/climate-change>

Mitigation Action Plan.

<https://www.croydon.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2022-01/climate-change-mitigation-action-plans.pdf>

Adaptation Plan.

<https://www.croydon.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2022-01/climate-change-adaptation-action-plans.pdf>

Denbighshire

Climate Change.

<https://www.denbighshire.gov.uk/en/environmental-health/climate-and-ecological-change/climate-and-ecological-change.aspx>

Climate and Ecological Change Strategy 2021/22 to 2029/30.

<https://www.denbighshire.gov.uk/en/your-council/strategies-plans-and-policies/strategies/climate-and-ecological-change-strategy.aspx>

Conwy Environmental resilience sub-group.

<https://conwyanddenbighshirelsb.org.uk/home/english-wellbeing-assessment/english-climate-change/>

Dumfries and Galloway

Carbon Neutral Strategic Plan

<https://www.dumgal.gov.uk/article/21773/Climate-Emergency>

Dundee City

Climate Action Plan.

<https://www.dundee.gov.uk/sites/default/files/publications/climateactionplan.pdf>

Homeowners guide to flood resilience.

https://lmkcorp1.s3.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/FloodGuide_ForHomeowners.pdf

Dundee's Discovery Point heritage centre.

<https://www.bbc.com/news/uk-scotland-tayside-central-58056237>

Ealing (London)

Ealing Council declared a climate emergency in April 2019.

https://www.ealing.gov.uk/info/201033/council_and_local_decisions/2691/climate_action/1#:~:text=Ealing%20Council%20declared%20a%20climate,and%20an%20organisation%20by%202030.

Grants for adapting homes. Climate Action.

https://www.ealing.gov.uk/download/downloads/id/1522/ealing_bap.pdf

https://www.ealing.gov.uk/info/201033/council_and_local_decisions/2691/climate_action/1

https://www.ealing.gov.uk/downloads/download/6005/climate_and_ecological_emergency_strategy

East Ayrshire

Clean Green East Ayrshire Climate Change Strategy. Council's carbon emissions in 2020/21.

<https://www.east-ayrshire.gov.uk/News/article/keeping-up-momentum-in-the-race-to-cut-carbon-emissions>

[https://docs.east-](https://docs.east-ayrshire.gov.uk/crpadmmin/2012%20AGENDAS/COUNCIL/24%20JUNE%202021/East%20Ayrshire%20Climate%20Change%20Strategy.pdf)

[ayrshire.gov.uk/crpadmmin/2012%20AGENDAS/COUNCIL/24%20JUNE%202021/East%20Ayrshire%20Climate%20Change%20Strategy.pdf](https://docs.east-ayrshire.gov.uk/crpadmmin/2012%20AGENDAS/COUNCIL/24%20JUNE%202021/East%20Ayrshire%20Climate%20Change%20Strategy.pdf)

Eastbourne (Lewes and Eastbourne)

Climate Change.

<https://www.lewes-eastbourne.gov.uk/community/lewes-district-climate-change-and-sustainability/>

Climate Change and Sustainability Strategy 2021.

https://www.lewes-eastbourne.gov.uk/_resources/assets/inline/full/0/315922.pdf

Climate Adaptation Group.

<https://ecoactioneb.co.uk/action/climate-adaptation-group>

Carbon Neutral 2020.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/eastbourne-borough-council-2e357ba.pdf>

East Lindsey

Climate Change.

<https://www.e-lindsey.gov.uk/ClimateChange>

Enfield (London)

Climate Action Plan 2020. Climate Action Plan progress report and carbon emissions review 2020/21. Carbon Emissions Review 2019/20.

<https://new.enfield.gov.uk/services/environment/climate-action/>

#1 Retrofit London. Lead borough = LB Enfield and LB Waltham Forest.

https://www.city.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/641229/CU-CED-London-4.10.21.pdf

Forest Heath (now West Suffolk)

West Suffolk Environment and Climate Change Taskforce, Final Report 2020.

<https://democracy.westsuffolk.gov.uk/documents/s37876/CAB.WS.20.045%20West%20Suffolk%20Environment%20and%20Climate%20Change%20Taskforce%20-%20Final%20Report.pdf>

Environmental Statement 2020-2021.

<https://www.westsuffolk.gov.uk/protecting-our-environment/upload/Environmental-Statement-2020-21.pdf>

https://westsuffolk.inconsult.uk/WSLP_Issues_and_Options/viewCompoundDoc?docid=11737876&partid=11825940&pfv=y

Moves to make region climate-change resilient.

<https://www.eadt.co.uk/news/west-suffolk-moves-to-make-region-climate-change-resilient-2077000>

Glasgow City

Proposed Actions.

<https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/index.aspx?articleid=18318>

<https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/CHttpHandler.ashx?id=50623&p=0>

Cities Initiatives.

<https://www.glasgow.gov.uk/index.aspx?articleid=27334>

<https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2021/jun/29/billions-needed-to-protect-glasgow-from-climate-effects-report-says>

Climate Ready Clyde has developed Glasgow City Region's first Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan. Launched in June 2021.

<http://climatereadyclyde.org.uk/adaptation-strategy-and-action-plan/>

Great Yarmouth

Government Website.

<https://www.great-yarmouth.gov.uk/>

Greenwich (London)

In June 2019, the Council agreed a motion to declare a climate change emergency.

https://www.royalgreenwich.gov.uk/info/200327/climate_emergency/2166/what_is_the_climate_emergency

Greener Greenwich strategy.

https://www.royalgreenwich.gov.uk/info/200222/policies_and_plans/691/greener_greenwich_strategy

Carbon Neutral Plan.

https://www.royalgreenwich.gov.uk/info/200326/greener_greenwich

Hackney (London)

Climate Change.

<https://hackney.gov.uk/air-quality-and-climate-change>

Climate emergency declaration.

<https://hackney.gov.uk/climate-emergency-declaration>

Roadmap to net zero.

<https://news.hackney.gov.uk/download/1097088/hds14491-gh-a4leaflet4pp-oct21-web.pdf>

#2 Low carbon development. Lead borough = LB Hackney.

https://www.city.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/641229/CU-CED-London-4.10.21.pdf

Hammersmith and Fulham (London)

Climate and Ecology Strategy and Climate and Ecology Action Plan.

<https://www.lbhf.gov.uk/environment/climate-and-ecological-emergency>

Climate and Ecology Strategy.

http://democracy.lbhf.gov.uk/ieDecisionDetails.aspx?AIIId=65552&dm_t=0,0,0,0

Haringey (London)

On 9 March 2021, Haringey's Cabinet voted unanimously to adopt the Haringey Climate Change Action Plan (CCAP).

<https://www.haringey.gov.uk/environment-and-waste/going-green/net-zero-carbon-haringey>

https://www.haringey.gov.uk/sites/haringeygovuk/files/final_haringey_climate_change_action_plan_-_march_2021.pdf

Hastings

Climate Change.

<https://www.hastings.gov.uk/my-council/climate-change/>

Climate Emergency Strategy 2020.

https://www.hastings.gov.uk/content/my_council/decisions_how/policies_strategies/pdfs/Climate_Change_Strategy_March_2020.pdf

Action Plan 2020/21 to 2021/22.

https://www.hastings.gov.uk/content/my_council/decisions_how/policies_strategies/pdfs/Cabinet_Final_Climate_emergency_action_plan_march_2020_v2.pdf

Hillingdon

Strategic Climate Action Plan 2021.

<https://www.hillingdon.gov.uk/climate-action>

Hounslow (London)

Action Plan.

https://www.hounslow.gov.uk/info/20006/environment/2063/climate_emergency/2

Greener Borough Framework and flood risk strategy address adaptation strategies.

https://www.hounslow.gov.uk/info/20006/environment/2237/greener_borough_framework

https://www.hounslow.gov.uk/downloads/file/2926/hounslow_flood_risk_strategy

#6 Build the green economy. Lead borough = LB Hounslow.

https://www.city.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/641229/CU-CED-London-4.10.21.pdf

Inverclyde

Climate Action.

<https://www.inverclyde.gov.uk/planning-and-the-environment/climate-change/climate-change-adaptation#:~:text=Action%20on%20climate%20change%20adaptation,projects%20that%20help%20reduce%20flooding.>

Climate Ready Clyde has developed Glasgow City Region's first Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan. Launched in June 2021.

<http://climatereadyclide.org.uk/adaptation-strategy-and-action-plan/>

Isle of Anglesey

Government Website.

<https://carboncopy.eco/local-climate-action/isle-of-anglesey>

Islington (London)

Net Zero strategy. Islington Council declared a climate emergency in June 2019.

<https://www.islington.gov.uk/environment-and-energy/climate-emergency>

#4 Renewable power for London. Lead borough = LB Islington.

https://www.city.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/641229/CU-CED-London-4.10.21.pdf

Carbon Strategy.

<https://www.islington.gov.uk/~media/sharepoint-lists/public-records/energyservices/businessplanning/strategies/20202021/20201209vision2030islingtonzerocarbonstrategy1.pdf>

Kensington and Chelsea (London)

Air Quality and Climate Change Action Plan 2016 – 2021.

<https://www.rbkc.gov.uk/environment/climate-change/climate-change-strategies-and-action-plans#climate-change-strategies-and-action-plans>

Air Quality and Climate Change Action Plan 2016–2021 Appendices.

<https://www.rbkc.gov.uk/media/document/aqccap-technical-appendices>

Action Plan.

<https://www.rbkc.gov.uk/media/document/air-quality-and-climate-change-action-plan-v2-january-2019>

King's Lynn and West Norfolk

Climate Change.

https://www.west-norfolk.gov.uk/info/20095/energy_and_climate_change

2019 Climate commitments.

<https://democracy.west-norfolk.gov.uk/documents/s36830/Setting%20Climate%20Comittments%20for%20Kings%20Lynn%20and%20West%20Norfolk.pdf>

Emissions Reduction Strategy and Action Plan 2021 – 2024 Draft.

<https://democracy.west-norfolk.gov.uk/documents/s46806/Climate%20Change%20Strategy%20and%20Action%20Plan%20v.15%2019052021%20Climate%20Change%20Informal%20Working%20Group%20180.pdf>

Kingston upon Hull, City of

Proposed Climate Adaptation.

<https://www.hull.gov.uk/environment/climate-change/climate-adaptation>

Proposed strategic flood risk assessment.

<https://www.hull.gov.uk/environment/adverse-weather/strategic-flood-risk-assessment>

Carbon Neutral Hull.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/kingston-upon-hull-city-council-1536cba.pdf>

Knowsley

Climate Emergency Action Plan 2020.

<https://www.knowsley.gov.uk/knowsleycouncil/media/Documents/CLIMATE-EMERGENCY-ACTION-PLAN.pdf>

<https://www.knowsley.gov.uk/your-council/policies,-plans-and-strategies/place#enforcement-policy>

2008/09 and 2012-16 Council's Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan.

http://www.knowsley.gov.uk/pdf/climate_change_strategy.pdf

2012 Strategy.

<https://www.knowsley.gov.uk/pdf/knowsley-partnership-climate-change-strategy-2012-2016.pdf>

Gallery Takeover. Children Tackling Climate Change.

<https://www.knowsley.gov.uk/things-to-do/museums-and-galleries/exhibitions/gallery-takeover-children-tackling-climate-change>

Lambeth (London)

We recently became the first London council to declare a climate emergency and committed that the council will be carbon-neutral by 2030.

<https://www.lambeth.gov.uk/better-fairer-lambeth/climate-change-and-sustainability>

A carbon measurement framework and baseline will be produced by the council in 2020.

<https://beta.lambeth.gov.uk/environmental-services/climate-change-impact-and-plans/becoming-carbon-neutral-council-2030/implementation>

<https://beta.lambeth.gov.uk/environmental-services/climate-change>

Leicester

Climate strategy.

<https://www.leicester.gov.uk/your-council/policies-plans-and-strategies/environment-and-sustainability/climate-emergency/>

<https://www.leicester.gov.uk/media/dbxlmrxw/leicester-climate-emergency-full-strategy-2020-2023.pdf>

<https://www.leicester.gov.uk/media/tvnhl2pe/climate-emergency-action-plan-april-2020-to-march-2023.pdf>

Lewisham (London)

Climate Emergency Action Plan.

<https://lewisham.gov.uk/myservices/environment/making-the-borough-carbon-neutral-by-2030-climate-emergency-declaration>

Liverpool

Liverpool city plan.

<https://liverpool.gov.uk/communities-and-safety/action-on-climate-change/>

Net Zero plan.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/liverpool-city-council-fc4457e.pdf>

LFRRMS.

https://liverpool.gov.uk/media/1356897/local-flood-risk-management-strategy_final.pdf

Meeting Minutes Cabinet March 2021 including Low Carbon Route Map to Zero (2021).

<https://councillors.liverpool.gov.uk/documents/g18014/Public%20reports%20pack%2005th-Mar-2021%2009.00%20Cabinet%20201021.pdf?T=10>

Liverpool City Region Combined Authority

UK's first local climate resilience planning policy set for Liverpool City Region.

<https://www.edie.net/news/9/UK-s-first-local-climate-resilience-planning-policy-for-Liverpool-City-Region/>

Building Climate Resilience. Case Study.

<https://www.liverpoollep.org/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/Building-Climate-Resilience-in-Liverpool-City-Region-FINAL2017.pdf>

Strategic Planning for Climate Resilience. City Region.

<https://www.liverpoolcityregion-ca.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/RTPI-Climate-Resilience-Report.pdf>

Luton

Climate Change.

<https://m.luton.gov.uk/Page/Show/Environment/climate-change/Pages/default.aspx>

Climate Action Plan 2021.

<https://m.luton.gov.uk/Page/Show/Environment/climate-change/Pages/Climate-change-action-plan.aspx>

Climate Change Guide 2021.

<https://www.luton.gov.uk/Environment/Lists/LutonDocuments/PDF/Climate%20change/climate-change-guide.pdf>

Climate adaptation reporting third round. Luton Airport.

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/climate-adaptation-reporting-third-round-luton-airport>

Manchester

Climate Change Action Plan.

https://secure.manchester.gov.uk/info/500002/council_policies_and_strategies/3833/zero_carbon_manchester/4

Zero carbon.

https://secure.manchester.gov.uk/info/500002/council_policies_and_strategies/3833/zero-carbon_manchester

Manchester climate change framework.

<https://www.manchesterclimate.com/framework-2020-25>

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/councils/manchester-city-council/>

Adaptation and Resilience. Planning and Action for Manchester.

<https://www.ukclimateresilience.org/projects/adaptation-resilience-planning-action-for-manchester/>

5-Year Plan.

<https://www.greatermanchester-ca.gov.uk/what-we-do/environment/five-year-environment-plan/>

Climate adaptation. Urban Innovation. Funding.

<https://www.uia-initiative.eu/en/uia-cities/greater-manchester>

Merthyr Tydfil

Decarbonization.

<https://www.merthyr.gov.uk/council/decarbonisation/decarbonisation/>

Nature Recovery Action Plan 2019-2024.

<https://www.merthyr.gov.uk/media/5685/merthyr-tydfil-nature-recovery-action-plan-2019.pdf>

Carbon Management Plan (CMP) 2019.

<https://www.merthyr.gov.uk/media/6753/mcbbc-carbon-management-strategy-v05-final-july-2019.pdf>

Middlesbrough

Green Strategy.

<https://www.middlesbrough.gov.uk/environment-and-public-protection/green-strategy/our-green-action-plan>

2010 Middlesbrough's Climate Change Community Action Plan 2010-2020.

<https://www.middlesbrough.gov.uk/sites/default/files/Middlesbrough%E2%80%99s%20Climate%20Change%20Community%20Action%20Plan%202010-2020.pdf>

Major flood defence scheme completed.

<https://www.middlesbrough.gov.uk/news/major-flood-defence-scheme-completed>

Neath Port Talbot

Decarbonisation and Renewable Energy Strategy (DARE). Green infrastructure.

<https://www.npt.gov.uk/23524>

<https://www.npt.gov.uk/media/13541/dare-strategy-may-20.pdf?v=20200522162830>

<https://www.npt.gov.uk/media/9417/nptcbc-biodiversity-duty-plan.pdf?v=20190125155137>

Newham (London)

Climate Emergency Action Plan (PDF) (June 2020).

<https://www.newham.gov.uk/climatenow>

<https://www.newham.gov.uk/downloads/file/1883/climate-emergency-strategic-intent-report-2019>

<https://www.newham.gov.uk/public-health-safety/newham-climate-now-1/2?documentId=494&categoryId=20023>

<https://www.newham.gov.uk/downloads/file/1882/climate-emergency-action-plan>

Newport

Newport declares ecological and climate emergency.

<https://www.newport.gov.uk/en/Council-Democracy/News/articles/2021/November-2021/Newport-declares-ecological-and-climate-emergency.aspx>

Carbon Management Plan.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/newport-city-council-1ed3f15.pdf>

North Ayrshire

The Ayrshire Local Flood Risk Management Plan. Flood Risk Management Strategy.

<https://www.north-ayrshire.gov.uk/council/strategies-plans-and-policies/strategies-plans-and-policies.aspx>

North East Lincolnshire

Carbon Roadmap sets out how the Council can reach net zero emissions by 2040 and the borough by 2050. Proposed Natural Assets Plan (proposed for Dec 2021).

<https://www.nelincs.gov.uk/north-east-lincolnshire-councils-path-to-net-zero-and-a-better-environment-set-out-in-new-reports/>

Climate Local supports councils to reduce carbon emissions and increase resilience to a changing climate.

<https://www.nelincs.gov.uk/keeping-our-area-clean-and-safe/renewnel/climate-local/>

North Lanarkshire

In 2019, they declared a Climate Emergency and set a target of Net Zero for North Lanarkshire by 2030.

<https://www.northlanarkshire.gov.uk/your-community/working-communities/consultations/closed-consultations/climate-plan-act2030-take-survey#:~:text=In%202019%2C%20we%20declared%20a,for%20North%20Lanarkshire%20by%202030.&text=As%20a%20public%20sector%20body,climate%2Dready%20and%20act%20sustainably.>

Emergency Declaration.

<https://www.northlanarkshire.gov.uk/news/council-declares-ambition-climate-change>

ACT Now (Action on Climate Together) partnership to tackle climate change involving local schools, colleges, businesses, the local authority, the voluntary sector, Scottish Enterprise, NHS Lanarkshire, and the emergency services to curb the region's carbon emissions.

<https://www.northlanarkshire.gov.uk/news/climate-change-partnership-created>

ACT2030. DRAFT of Climate Plan. Regional Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan.

[https://www.northlanarkshire.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2021-](https://www.northlanarkshire.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2021-09/North%20Lanarkshire%27s%20Draft%20Climate%20Plan%20ACT2030.pdf)

[09/North%20Lanarkshire%27s%20Draft%20Climate%20Plan%20ACT2030.pdf](https://www.northlanarkshire.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2021-09/North%20Lanarkshire%27s%20Draft%20Climate%20Plan%20ACT2030.pdf)

North Somerset

Climate strategies.

<https://www.n-somerset.gov.uk/council-democracy/priorities-strategies/climate-emergency/our-plans-tackle-climate-change>

2011 resilience plan across sectors.

<https://www.n-somerset.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2020-03/Building%20resilience%20to%20extreme%20weather%20and%20climate%20change%20in%20North%20Somerset.pdf>

Healthier Together Estates Climate Change Adaptation Plan 2021-2025 for Bristol, North Somerset, and South Gloucestershire.

<https://bnssghealthiertogether.org.uk/documents/healthier-together-estates-climate-change-adaptation-plan-2021-2025/>

<https://www.n-somerset.gov.uk/council-democracy/priorities-strategies/climate-emergency/our-plans-tackle-climate-change>

<https://www.n-somerset.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2020-02/North%20Somerset%20climate%20emergency%20action%20plan.pdf>

<https://www.n-somerset.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2020-02/North%20Somerset%20climate%20emergency%20strategy%202019.pdf>

<https://www.n-somerset.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2020-02/North%20Somerset%20climate%20emergency%20strategy%202019.pdf>

<https://www.n-somerset.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2020-02/North%20Somerset%20climate%20emergency%20strategy%202019.pdf>

Nottingham

2020 Carbon Neutral Nottingham 2020 – 2028 Action Plan.

<https://www.nottinghamcity.gov.uk/media/2619917/2028-carbon-neutral-action-plan-v2-160620.pdf>

Carbon Neutral Charter 2028.

<https://www.nottinghamcity.gov.uk/media/2620252/nottinghams-2028-carbon-neutral-charter-3.pdf>

Oldham

Climate Change Strategy (LINK BROKEN)

https://www.oldham.gov.uk/info/200579/environmental_policies_and_plans/2158/climate_change

Green New Deal Strategy 2020-25.

<https://www.oldham.gov.uk/gnds>

Topic Paper Issues. Adaptation needs to be added to Local Plan

https://www.oldham.gov.uk/downloads/file/7028/climate_change_topic_paper

Orkney Islands

Climate Change.

<https://www.orkney.gov.uk/Council/C/orkney-climate-aware.htm>

<https://www.orkney.gov.uk/News?postid=4612>

2015 Carbon Management Programme 2016-26.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/orkney-islands-council-56bf6fd.pdf>

Climate Change Duties. Report by Executive Director of Development and Infrastructure.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/orkney-islands-council-f4cfe98.pdf>

Oxford

Climate Emergency.

<https://www.oxford.gov.uk/climate-emergency>

Zero Carbon Road Map.

https://www.oxford.gov.uk/downloads/download/1241/zero_carbon_oxford_partnership_road_map_and_action_plan

Action Plan.

https://www.oxford.gov.uk/downloads/download/1221/zero_carbon_action_plan

Oxford Citizens Assembly on Climate Change.

https://www.oxford.gov.uk/info/20011/environment/1343/oxford_citizens_assembly_on_climate_change

Redbridge (London)

Climate change.

<https://www.redbridge.gov.uk/about-the-council/climate-change/>

Action Plan (2021).

<https://www.redbridge.gov.uk/media/9400/appendix-b-climate-change-action-plan-final.pdf>

Local Plan.

<https://www.redbridge.gov.uk/planning-and-building/planning-policy/local-plan/>

Climate change Corporate Panel Report.

file:///Z:/Personal/RRU/envp691_research_paper/working/sources/adaptation_risk_assessment/top_ranked_areas/london_and_boroughs/london-borough-of-redbridge-6cc4de5.pdf

Renfrewshire

They declared a climate emergency in Renfrewshire in 2019 and aim for net-zero emissions by 2030.

<https://www.renfrewshire.gov.uk/article/11998/Meet-our-Climate-Emergency-Lead-Officer-Roz-Smith#:~:text=We%20declared%20a%20climate%20emergency.net%2Dzero%20emissions%20by%202030.&text=Climate%20change%20itself%20cannot%20be%20stopped%2C%20but%20it%20can%20be%20slowed.>

<https://www.renfrewshire.gov.uk/article/11733/Climate-Change-projects-to-make-Renfrewshire-net-zero>

Climate Change Sub-Committee. Climate Change Action Fund. Edinburgh Declaration.

Renfrewshire's plan for net zero. Renfrewshire Climate Panel. Partner campaigns.

<https://www.renfrewshire.gov.uk/article/11733/Climate-Change-projects-to-make-Renfrewshire-net-zero>

Climate Ready Clyde has developed Glasgow City Region's first Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan. Launched in June 2021.

<http://climatereadyclyde.org.uk/adaptation-strategy-and-action-plan/>

News Recognition.

<https://www.heraldscotland.com/politics/19784821.innovation-central-tackling-climate-change-renfrewshire/>

They have not yet published our Plan for Net-Zero. Proposed climate-changing plan.

Establishment of the Renfrewshire Climate Panel.

<https://www.the-gazette.co.uk/news/19894983.renfrewshire-council-urged-speed-efforts-tackle-climate-change/>

Rhondda Cynon Taf

Climate Declaration.

<https://www.rctcbc.gov.uk/EN/GetInvolved/Campaigns/ClimateChangeRCT/TacklingClimateChangeRCT.aspx>

Local Development Plan.

<https://www.bridgend.gov.uk/media/1413/bd27.pdf>

<https://rctcbc.moderngov.co.uk/documents/s25520/Appendix%20A.pdf?LLL=0>

Rochdale

Climate Change.

<http://www.rochdale.gov.uk/pests-pollution-and-food/climate-change/Pages/tackling-climate-change.aspx>

Pre-plan 2020-25 Plan of Action Draft.

<http://www.rochdale.gov.uk/pdf/2020-12-22-draft-climate-change-strategy-v7.pdf>

Runnymede

Climate Change.

<https://www.runnymede.gov.uk/climate-reports-statistics-1>

Local Plan.

<https://www.runnymede.gov.uk/climate-reports-statistics-1/climate-related-policies-strategies>

Climate and sustainability.

<https://www.runnymede.gov.uk/green-runnymede/climate-sustainability>

Sandwell

Climate Change.

https://www.sandwell.gov.uk/info/200274/pollution/4402/climate_change_and_air_quality_in_sandwell

Climate Change Strategy 2020-41.

https://www.sandwell.gov.uk/download/downloads/id/31151/climate_change_strategy.pdf

Tackling climate change in Sandwell.

<https://www.expressandstar.com/news/education/2020/01/21/sandwell-moves-to-tackle-climate-change-issues/>

Sedgemoor

Sedgemoor Climate Emergency Strategy & Action Plan.

<https://www.sedgemoor.gov.uk/article/4093/Climate-Change>

Shepway (Folkestone and Hythe)

Folkestone & Hythe District Council declared a climate emergency in 2019. Briefing Note.

<https://www.folkestone-hythe.gov.uk/climatechange>

<https://folkestone-hythe.gov.uk/article/1735/Climate-Change-and-Ecological-Emergency-briefing-note>

Carbon Action Plan.

https://folkestone-hythe.gov.uk/media/3365/Carbon-Action-Plan/pdf/F_HDC_Carbon_Action_Plan.pdf?m=637511455571400000

Slough

In July 2019 Slough Borough Council declared a political motion on climate change.

<https://www.slough.gov.uk/strategies-plans-policies/climate-change/2#:~:text=In%20July%202019%20Slough%20Borough,from%20our%20estate%20and%20operations>

Climate Change strategy and action plan (2021).

<https://www.slough.gov.uk/downloads/file/2279/slough-borough-council-climate-change-strategy-action-plan-report-final>

Carbon management Plan.

<https://www.slough.gov.uk/downloads/file/922/carbon-management-plan-2020-2030>

South Holland

South Holland District Council wants resident views on Climate Change Strategy.

<https://www.sholland.gov.uk/article/18596/South-Holland-District-Council-wants-resident-views-on-Climate-Change-Strategy>

Link to strategy BROKEN (after Feb 4).

<https://www.sholland.gov.uk/ClimateConsultation>

Climate Change Strategy Plan Draft.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/south-holland-district-council-3114f55.pdf>

Southwark (London)

They declared a climate emergency in March 2019. Carbon neutral by 2050 to 2030.

<https://moderngov.southwark.gov.uk/ieListDocuments.aspx?CIId=132&MIId=6096&Ver=4>

Climate strategy and action plan.

<https://www.southwark.gov.uk/environment/climate-emergency>

#7 Creating a resilient and green London. Lead borough = LB Southwark.

https://www.city.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/641229/CU-CED-London-4.10.21.pdf

Report Appendices.

[https://moderngov.southwark.gov.uk/documents/s99899/Appendix%20B%20Techncial%20ap](https://moderngov.southwark.gov.uk/documents/s99899/Appendix%20B%20Techncial%20appendix.pdf)

[pendix.pdf](https://moderngov.southwark.gov.uk/documents/s99899/Appendix%20B%20Techncial%20appendix.pdf)

Climate Strategy.

<https://www.southwark.gov.uk/assets/attach/48607/Climate-Change-Strategy-July-2021-.pdf>

Swale

Climate Scorecard.

<https://swale.gov.uk/news-and-your-council/news-and-campaigns/latest-news/climate-scorecard>

Meeting minutes to action plan.

<https://services.swale.gov.uk/meetings/mgAi.aspx?ID=8535>

Climate & Ecological Emergency Action Plan (2020).

<https://swale.gov.uk/news-and-your-council/news-and-campaigns/latest-news/cee-update>

Climate Emergency.

<https://services.swale.gov.uk/assets/Climate-Change-and-Ecological-Emergency/SBC%20CEE%20Action%20Plan%20Final%20with%20illustrations.pdf>

Action Pan.

https://services.swale.gov.uk/meetings/documents/s14486/SBC%20CEE%20Action%20Plan%20Final_.pdf

Teignbridge

Declared climate emergency.

<https://www.teignbridge.gov.uk/environmental-health-and-wellbeing/climate-change/climate-change-emergency/>

Housing strategy and transport local plan. Green Network Strategy. Local plan.

<https://www.teignbridge.gov.uk/council-and-democracy/council-information/strategies-policies-and-performance/strategies-and-plans/>

Draft Action Plan.

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/teignbridge-district-council-f164414.pdf>

Action on Climate in Teignbridge. Case study.

<https://www.local.gov.uk/case-studies/action-climate-teignbridge-conversations-make-difference>

Council PM speaker at Risk, Resilience and Responses in a Changing Climate.

<https://www.floodandcoast.com/assets/Uploads/FC18-EVENT-PREVIEW.pdf>

Thanet

Climate Change.

<https://www.thanet.gov.uk/services/energy-and-climate-change/>

Climate Change Action Plan

<https://data.climateemergency.uk/media/data/plans/thanet-district-council-391e372.pdf>

Kent Environment Strategy.

<https://www.kent.gov.uk/about-the-council/strategies-and-policies/environment-waste-and-planning-policies/environmental-policies/kent-environment-strategy>

Local Plan.

<https://www.thanet.gov.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/Thanet-Local-Plan-July-2020-1-1.pdf>

Thurrock

Climate Change.

<https://www.thurrock.gov.uk/greenhouse-gases/climate-change>

Thurrock Climate Change Scoping Study.

<https://democracy.thurrock.gov.uk/documents/s29309/Thurrock%20Climate%20Change%20Strategy%20-%20Appendix%201%20Thurrock%20Climate%20Change%20Scoping%20Study%20Report.pdf>

Thurrock Design Strategy Supplementary Planning Document (2017).

<https://www.thurrock.gov.uk/sites/default/files/assets/documents/designstrategy-planning-201703-v01.pdf>

Torfaen

Climate Change.

<https://www.torfaen.gov.uk/en/AboutTheCouncil/Climate-change/Climate-change-and-nature-emergency.aspx>

Tackling Torfaen's carbon emissions.

<https://www.torfaen.gov.uk/en/News/2021/October/25-Tackling-Torfaens-carbon-emissions.aspx>

Plans for “climate ambassadors” network kickstarted.

<https://www.torfaen.gov.uk/en/News/2021/November/Plans-for-climate-ambassadors-network-kickstarted.aspx>

Tower Hamlets (London)

The mayor declared a climate emergency in March 2019.

https://www.towerhamlets.gov.uk/lgnl/environment_and_waste/Sustainability/Climate_emergency.aspx

Net zero Carbon Plan.

<https://democracy.towerhamlets.gov.uk/mgConvert2PDF.aspx?ID=165906>

No specific climate change adaptation strategy. However, it carries out several activities that work towards adapting to climate change.

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/cy/request/197659/response/493377/attach/3/FOI%2010066%20Climate%20change%20adaptation%20strategy.pdf?cookie_passthrough=1

Waltham Forest (London)

Climate emergency declaration.

<https://democracy.walthamforest.gov.uk/mgAi.aspx?ID=32233>

Council aims to finally publish its plan in spring this year.

<https://walthamforestecho.co.uk/why-waltham-forest-got-a-zero-on-its-climate-plan-scorecard>

#1 Retrofit London. Lead borough = LB Enfield and LB Waltham Forest.

https://www.city.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/641229/CU-CED-London-4.10.21.pdf

Warrington

Climate emergency commission.

<https://www.warrington.gov.uk/climate-emergency>

Climate Plans.

<https://www.warrington.gov.uk/our-climate-emergency-plans-and-targets>

Green energy strategy.

https://www.warrington.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2020-02/green_energy_strategy.pdf

Meeting Agenda (2019).

https://www.warrington.gov.uk/sites/default/files/2020-07/full_council_-_17_june_2019_-_agenda_pack.pdf

West Dunbartonshire

Climate Change Strategy and Action Plan for West Dunbartonshire.

<https://www.west-dunbarton.gov.uk/council/strategies-plans-and-policies/council-wide-plans-and-strategies/sustainable-development/climate-change/>

Member of Climate Ready Clyde. The Council participated in Climate Week in 2016/17.

https://sustainablesotlandnetwork.org/slickr_media_upload?id=397

Climate Ready Clyde has developed Glasgow City Region's first Adaptation Strategy and Action Plan. Launched in June 2021.

<http://climatereadyclyde.org.uk/adaptation-strategy-and-action-plan/>

West Lindsey

Climate strategy and action plan.

<https://www.west-lindsey.gov.uk/my-services/my-community/sustainability-climate-change-and-environment/>

Westminster (London)

Declared climate emergency. By 2023, develop a Climate Adaptation Plan.

<https://www.westminster.gov.uk/tackling-climate-change-westminster/our-climate-action-plan>

Climate Strategy (2013-18).

https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/197625/response/487331/attach/4/Climate%20Resilience%20and%20Adaptation%20Framework%20Final.pdf?cookie_passthrough=1

#3 Low carbon transport. Lead borough = RB Kingston and City of Westminster.

https://www.city.ac.uk/_data/assets/pdf_file/0006/641229/CU-CED-London-4.10.21.pdf

Climate Change Projects.

<https://www.westminster.gov.uk/tackling-climate-change-westminster/climate-change-projects>

West Somerset (Somerset West and Taunton)

Climate Emergency.

<https://www.somersetwestandtaunton.gov.uk/climate-emergency/>

Climate emergency Strategy.

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Appendix D

Checklist for Evaluation of Climate Action of Local Authorities

Category	Criteria	Yes	No, but in progress	Not evident/ sufficient
1 – Adaptation strategy/action plan for heat/flooding in place	Has LA an adaptation plan or strategies for flooding? Can be part of a climate plan or any other plan but it needs to contain specific adaptation actions (at least one, implemented or proposed)	2	1	0
2 – Climate strategy, mitigation, or carbon reduction plan in place	Has district any type of climate plan/strategy, mitigation or Net Zero plan, route-map, or policy?	2	1	0
3 – Passed climate emergency declaration	Is district identified on Climate Emergency UK website?	2		0
4 – Other adaptation actions	With or without adaptation plan in place, are there other adaptation actions, e.g., offers training, community engagement, community groups, flood defence schemes, or flood risk management, case studies, climate initiatives, workshops? At least one.	2	1	0
5 – Website easy to navigate and helpful	Is there a climate change tab or basic info on climate change, contact information, offers help with process, links to resources, invites public to engage, or suggests action? At least three.	2	1	0

Appendix E

Climate Emergency UK Scoring System

Scorecard Section	Criteria
1 - Governance, Development and Funding	- examines who will lead the plan, the net-zero targets, the council's commitment to the plan, funding and costing, council limits and monitoring, reviewing, and updating the plan.
2 - Mitigation and Adaptation	- considers how well the plan outlines the implications of climate change on the local area, and whether the plan has set out strategies for decarbonising and adapting within the key areas of planning and land use, transport, infrastructure, business and industry, energy generation, heating, natural environment and biodiversity, and food systems and agriculture.
3 - Commitment and Integration	- assesses the integration of the climate and ecological emergency into the council's existing policies and procedures, as well as the target dates set out by the plan.
4 - Community Engagement and Communications	- questions who has been involved in the plan's development and how the council intends to keep the community involved in its delivery. It asks about the use of citizens' assemblies, what effort has been made to include under-represented groups, collaborative partnerships, how easy the plan is to find on the website, how well it is structured and whether there is a clear communication strategy.

5 - Measuring and Setting Emissions Targets	- concentrates on the emissions data and targets set out in the plan. Is there a baseline emissions inventory? Are emissions broken down into scope 1, 2 and 3 emissions? Are GHG emissions quantified? Does the plan prioritise emissions reductions over carbon offsetting?
6 - Co-benefits	- asks whether the plan considers the co-benefits of climate action and the public health risks of climate change.
7 - Diversity and Social Inclusion	- centres on whether the plan outlines which parts of the population will be most harmed by climate change, how it intends to focus resources to support vulnerable communities and whether it recognises that councils and residents have differing responsibilities for climate action.
8 - Education, Skills and Training	- focuses on carbon literacy training for all staff and councillors, education for the public, and training/upskilling the workforce.
9 - Ecological Emergency	- looks at the plan's commitments to tackling the ecological emergency. Does the plan include actions to address the ecological emergency? Does it focus on nature-based solutions? Are the ecological impacts of climate change mitigation actions considered?

Note. The scoring system consists of 9 sections, comprising 28 questions which together contain 73 sub-points. 78 marks are available for all councils, except for County Councils and Combined Authorities where 76 marks are available as question 11 does not apply. There are more marks than there are sub-points because some questions are worth more than 1 point. From “Council Climate Plan Scorecards” by Climate Emergency UK, n.d.-a, (<https://councilclimatescorecards.uk/methodology/#sec-gov>). In the public domain.